

COPING WITH TECHNOLOGY-RELATED CHALLENGES AMONG ADULTS AGED 55+ IN TASHKENT

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Abstract. *In recent years, technology has developed significantly; nevertheless, middle-aged and older people are facing technology-related issues. This report discusses the challenges faced by elderly citizens in Tashkent regarding technology and the coping strategies they use to overcome these challenges. The study specifically focuses on residents aged 55 and above, as this demographic is likely to have the most difficulty adapting to new technology. Six residents of Tashkent aged over 55 were interviewed for this study. The interview results reveal that senior generation people have several problems with technology issues, such as ordering a taxi and making online payments. The study concludes that seniors face challenges with technology integration in daily life. Coping skills like seeking support from loved ones, maintaining a positive attitude towards technology, and simplifying interfaces can help overcome these obstacles. Caregivers and technology developers should create solutions suited to seniors' needs, enhancing their tech literacy and engagement.*

Keywords: *elderly people, IT challenges, personal traits, family contribution, cellphones, ordering a taxi, making online payments*

Introduction

Tashkent has undergone rapid development and modernization in recent years. This has resulted in significant changes in the lifestyle and culture of its residents, particularly in the adoption and use of technology. While younger generations in Tashkent have readily adopted technology, the older generation has faced challenges in keeping pace with the rapid pace of technological change. This has raised questions about how these demographics cope with technology-related challenges and what strategies they use to adapt to these changes. The objective of this research is to examine the strategies that elderly Tashkent citizens use to confront difficulties associated with technology. The study aims to provide insights into how the aging population deals with technological advancements that have transformed society. The study focuses specifically on residents aged 55 and above, as this demographic is likely to have the most difficulty adapting to new technology. The study explores the different types of technology-related challenges faced by older Tashkent residents, as well as the

coping strategies that they use to overcome these challenges. The study reviews challenges faced by older adults in using technology, followed by research methodology including sample size, data collection and analysis techniques. Qualitative data and relevant statistics are presented as findings. The study concludes with a discussion on implications for policy and practice.

Literature Review

As technology becomes more incorporated into everyday life, those over the age of 55 encounter distinct obstacles in adjusting to it. Until recently, research has examined the interaction between technology and the elderly, concentrating on how they manage these obstacles. The literature review examines recent studies and findings of how individuals over the age of 55 deal with technological obstacles.

Factors that influence coping strategies

Technology may be of enormous service to the elderly, but it can also provide obstacles, particularly for those who are less comfortable with it. Many aspects, including personal traits, perceived utility and simplicity of use, social support, attitudes towards technology, and environmental factors, impact the coping mechanisms of the elderly, according to research done by Peek et al. (2014). In addition, Chéron and Kohlbacher (2018) demonstrated that consumer innovation is severely impacted by technological fear. This demonstrates that elderly individuals attempt to avoid new advances in their life. Knowing these aspects may assist carers and technology developers in designing strategies and solutions adapted to the requirements and preferences of senior people, therefore enhancing their quality of life. Nevertheless, Petrovčič et al. (2018) found that elderly persons continue to choose feature phones over smart phones. Yet, the mobile phone industry has grown diverse, with distinct socio-demographic and life-course characteristics for older buyers of feature phones and smartphones (Petrovčič et al. 2018).

Coping strategies for technology-related challenges

When senior users of technology meet hurdles, coping methods play a significant role in assisting them to overcome these obstacles. Peek et al. (2014) noted that when older persons meet technical issues, they may seek support from family, friends, or caretakers, or they might attempt to learn and utilize technology via trial and error. Having good attitudes about technology, such as seeing it as a tool for social connection or mental stimulation, may assist with maintaining motivation. In addition, Peek et al. (2014) observed that simplifying technology by using easier interfaces, bigger fonts, and fewer features may aid in preventing misunderstanding and dissatisfaction. By using these coping mechanisms, senior citizens may increase their technological literacy and reap the advantages of digital communication and involvement.

Adoption and use of technology among the elderly is an increasingly important problem in contemporary culture. Bae et al. (2020) discovered that knowledge of age-related changes may lower older persons' propensity to accept innovative items. In addition, the research revealed that older persons who feel stereotyped may restrict their innovativeness to avoid displaying ineptitude. These results show that age-related preconceptions must be addressed to improve technology adoption among the elderly. Chéron and Kohlbacher (2018) discovered in separate research that innovativeness is positively correlated with the adoption of high-tech advances, highlighting the need to develop a proactive attitude towards technology adoption among the elderly.

In conclusion, seniors face challenges with technology integration in daily life. Coping skills like seeking support from loved ones, maintaining a positive attitude towards technology, and simplifying interfaces can help overcome these obstacles. Factors such as personal traits, perceived usefulness and ease of use, social support, attitudes, and environment affect seniors' ability to cope. Encouraging proactive technology adoption and addressing age-related biases can improve their quality of life. However, there is a lack of research on this topic; therefore, we are going to explore how individuals over the age of 55 deal with technological obstacles.

Methods

The study aimed to explore how the elderly population in Tashkent, deals with technology-related challenges in their daily lives in Tashkent. The study employed a qualitative research design to collect data through semi-structured interviews with a sample of elderly individuals over the age of 55 in Tashkent.

The study targeted 6 participants (R1-R6), three males and three females, all of whom were 55 years old or older and from Tashkent, and had experienced technology-related challenges. Participants were recruited, with efforts made to ensure that participants were from different backgrounds and had varied experiences with technology. The interviews were conducted face-to-face and lasted between 4-7 minutes.

The interviews were conducted in Uzbek, and were translated to English. Prior to the interview, participants were informed about the confidentiality of their responses and the purpose of the research. They were asked for their permission to audio record the interviews, which were transcribed for analysis purposes.

The transcribed interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. The data were coded and categorized to identify patterns and themes that emerged from the interviews. The themes were organized into a narrative that provided an understanding of how the elderly population in Tashkent coped with technology-related challenges.

The qualitative approach through semi-structured interviews provided an in-depth understanding of how elderly people in Tashkent coped with technology-related

challenges. The use of audio recording and transcription allowed for accurate and thorough analysis of the data. The study's results can be used to develop interventions and strategies that can help the elderly population in Tashkent better cope with technology-related challenges.

Results

This section will reveal outcomes of the issue how older generation of Tashkent cope with technology-related problems. In this section findings are analyzed and illustrated.

All the participants reported using cellphones as their primary device, with all of them using Chinese phones like Redmi and Xiaomi. In addition to cellphones, respondents also used TV-sets, tablets, computers, and electric ovens.

The main uses of cellphones reported by participants were communication, watching videos via YouTube, chatting with friends, using the internet, and staying updated on news via Telegram groups. The main functions of cellphones reported by participants were chatting through Telegram, communication with people, watching videos, using the internet, following news, and using electronic notes. One elderly female participant expressed following (R1):

“I usually talk through cellphone. I use Telegram, watch different channels on YouTube, follow and read news, and chat with my friends.” (translated from Uzbek)

All the respondents reported being able to use their phones appropriately, but some participants faced issues with network outages, ordering taxis, making online payments, and registering for different apps. Only one participant reported having a few problems with cellphones, while the remaining five reported numerous issues with their phone (R2).

In addition, participants had problem with ordering taxi and making online payments as well. 2 out of 6 respondents could not order taxis and make online payments, while the other two could use them (R3 and R5). Two older participants reported being able to use both taxi ordering and online payments (R2- R3). The primary reason for these issues was a lack of experience. All participants who ordered taxis used the same app, YandexGo, while those who made online payments used apps like Click, Payme, and Milliy. Most participants who ordered taxis struggled with the same problem of inputting the correct destination location. Only one respondent who made online payments reported having no issues with the process (R2), while the others found the apps confusing to use. Children, grandsons and granddaughters, and daughter-in-law were the individuals who helped respondents solve technology-related problems. One respondent stated (R1):

“Mostly, humans should work on self-study and study with ambition. If something is unclear, they should ask for provide explanation from the children. If a

person has an ambition and convenient conditions, they will work on themselves, then he/she could succeed.” (translated from Uzbek)

Finally, for improving their digital literacy skills, participants reported self-study and learning from family members, such as their children, grandchildren, and daughter-in-law, to be beneficial.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that over 55 people have several problems with technology issues, such as ordering a taxi and making online payments. In addition, all respondents use Chinese modern cellphones. Finally, their family members are the main contributors to their level of digital literacy.

Discussion

The study aimed to explore how the elderly population in Tashkent deals with technology-related challenges in their daily lives. The qualitative research design allowed for an in-depth understanding of how elderly people in Tashkent coped with technology-related challenges.

The study's results reveal that all the participants reported using cellphones as their primary device, with all of them using Chinese phones like Redmi and Xiaomi. So, the statement of Petrovčič et al. (2018) was confirmed, that elderly people will continue using smartphones, while all participants use modern smartphones. The main uses of cellphones reported by participants were communication, watching videos via YouTube, chatting with friends, using the internet, and staying updated on news via Telegram groups. However, some participants face issues with ordering taxis, making online payments, and registering for different apps due to a lack of experience. They reported that this was because they did not have an interest in doing these activities, and they expressed that the age factor could be the root cause of technology issues.

The literature review reveals that seniors face distinct challenges in integrating technology into their daily lives. Factors such as personal traits, perceived usefulness and ease of use, social support, attitudes, and environment affect their ability to cope with technology-related challenges. The results of the research are similar to the study of Peek et al. (2014), who emphasized the coping mechanisms of elderly people. Coping skills such as seeking support from loved ones, maintaining a positive attitude towards technology, and simplifying interfaces can help seniors overcome these obstacles. Encouraging proactive technology adoption and addressing age-related biases can improve their quality of life. Peek et al. (2014) mentioned these coping strategies for the older generation, which means the findings from the investigation are a confirmation of their statements.

The main functions of cellphones reported by participants were chatting through Telegram, communication with people, watching videos, using the internet, following news, and checking the weather. The study also found that participants faced challenges

with using technology, such as difficulty navigating technology, fear of breaking the device, and difficulty typing due to small keyboards. Participants coped with these challenges by seeking support from family and friends and attempting to learn and utilize technology through trial and error. Most likely, it is because family members are the closest people in their lives. The study has several limitations, such as a small sample size and limited geographic scope. The study also only explored the coping strategies of seniors in Tashkent, and the results may not be generalizable to other populations. Nevertheless, the study provides valuable insights into how seniors cope with technology-related challenges in Tashkent, which can inform the development of interventions and strategies to improve seniors' quality of life.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the challenges that the elderly population faces in integrating technology into their daily lives. The study found that personal traits, perceived usefulness and ease of use, social support, attitudes, and environment affect seniors' ability to cope with technological challenges. The research investigated that senior people in Tashkent struggle with ordering a taxi and making online payments. Also, one of the interesting findings was that all participants use Chinese cellphones. Coping mechanisms like seeking support from loved ones, maintaining a positive attitude towards technology, and simplifying interfaces can help overcome these obstacles. The methodology employed in this study, which used semi-structured interviews to collect qualitative data, provides an in-depth understanding of how elderly people in Tashkent cope with technology-related challenges. The study's results can be used to develop interventions and strategies that can help the elderly population in Tashkent better cope with technology-related challenges. Overall, the findings of this study can be useful for policymakers and technology companies to design user-friendly apps and digital products that cater to the needs of older adults and address their technological challenges.

Recommendations

The elderly population can benefit greatly from technology, but several challenges need to be addressed

- Improving technology adoption among the elderly, phone developers should create user-friendly interfaces that are easy to navigate and understand. Simplifying payment systems to make them more accessible and creating customized technology solutions to meet the unique needs and preferences of elderly people.
- Additionally, providing regular technology training sessions can help elderly people understand how to use modern technology. Also, assisting their senior relatives regularly and teaching them how to use modern technology are other ways that family

members can help. Utilizing feature phones and supporting ride-hailing services can also help elderly people overcome mobility challenges and remain independent.

- The benefits of technology for the aged population should be promoted more widely, and governments should offer resources to assist the elderly in overcoming technological barriers.
- Finally, addressing age-related biases is also important, as stereotypes about the elderly can discourage technology adoption.

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